

THE MAIN STAGES OF IMPROVING THE SKILLS OF USING ELEMENTS OF HISTORICISM BY FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. *The article reveals the importance of historicism elements in mathematics lessons in elementary grades. The author demonstrates opportunities to increase students' interest in learning mathematics and in-depth study of the facts being studied.*

Keywords: *Elements of history, mathematical terminology and symbols, historical materials.*

From the first days of independence, the policy of reforming the education system as a key part of the course of reforms and renewal of society in Uzbekistan has been consistently pursued. To achieve this goal, the National Training Program was adopted, which provides for "... the implementation of the national model of training, the creation of socio-economic, legal, psychological and pedagogical conditions for the formation of a comprehensively developed personality, adaptation to modern changing society." and is being implemented successfully. This is also stated in the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis: "... We have set ourselves the goal of joining a number of developed countries and we will be able to achieve it only by carrying out accelerated reforms, relying on science, education and innovation. To do this, we, first of all, need to educate cadres of a new formation, who are the initiators of reforms, who have a strategic vision, deep knowledge and high qualifications. That is why we have begun reforming all levels of education - from preschool to higher education.

Science and education are very important to increase the intellectual and spiritual potential not only of young people, but of our society as a whole. Where science is underdeveloped, there is regression and backwardness in all areas of society.

The great thinkers of the East said: "The greatest wealth is reason and science, the greatest inheritance is a good upbringing, the greatest poverty is the lack of knowledge." The desire to master modern knowledge, be enlightened and have a high culture should become a vital need for all of us."

The topic of my scientific research work is "Improving the technology of using historical materials in primary grades (for example lessons of mathematics)" It consists of three chapters. The relevance of my work is based on the theory that one of the main ways to improve the effectiveness of the elementary school math class is to use historical data. Because we should try to bring up the young generation with a great feeling of proud of our nation and its history.

The purpose of the study. Elaboration of the content, forms and methods of using historical materials to improve the efficiency of elementary school mathematics, and the creation of an entire system. The object of the study is the process of using historical materials in the elementary school math class.

The subject of the study is to think about the structure of historical materials that enhance the effectiveness of math lessons.

According to the purpose and practical hypothesis the following tasks have been set:

1. To determine the current state of the curriculum and textbooks in the formation of historical concepts in elementary school mathematics.
2. Creating criteria for establishing students' sense of historical knowledge in teaching mathematics and enhancing classroom effectiveness.
3. To study the psycho-pedagogical aspects of historical knowledge in mathematics lessons.
4. To develop the best ways to teach students using math lessons through math lessons and test it through experimental.
5. To develop scientific methodological recommendations according to the research.

Scientific novelty of the research is:

- The use of historical materials in elementary school math lessons has always been proven through experimental testing.
- Criteria for determining the level of access by elementary school students to historical materials were developed.
- Methodological recommendations on the development and promotion of spiritual education of elementary school students.

Theoretical significance of the research:

- a new approach to primary education based on the linking of historical materials with teaching;

- Theoretical and substantiation of the content of activities aimed at the education of primary school students through the teaching of historical materials. Practical significance of the research: - The development of scientific and pedagogical recommendations for linking elementary school mathematics lessons with historical materials can increase its effectiveness.

- Parents, teachers and the general public are encouraged to use instruction in the use of historical materials in elementary school math classes to educate students as educated and perfect people.

The inseparable interdependence and unity of the tasks of forming the dialectical worldview of students, the tasks of their comprehensive education and development - all this is a conclusion about the appropriateness and expediency of the use of historical and mathematical materials in the study of modern school mathematics allows you to do. Indeed, the importance of familiarizing students with the history of science is well known for educating students in the spirit of patriotism and internationalism. The example of the life of great thinkers of the past, their scientific and moral convictions can have a strong influence on the processes of self-improvement and self-education of schoolchildren... For example, the genius scientist Biruni, who is known for outstanding discoveries in the field of astronomy, mathematics, geography, geology, botany, went down in the history of mankind as an outstanding humanist philosopher and poet. What gave strength to the discoveries of Biruni for the subsequent development of sciences and the practical use of the scientific results obtained by him? There is no doubt that his conviction in the importance of pure knowledge and search for the improvement of man was great. The main thing for Biruni was to learn and understand. Apparently, to put this fact at the heart of the moral beliefs of schoolchildren in the modern teacher should be no less than to acquaint students with his scientific work.

When combined with the study of the educational material of the school mathematics course, historical information is well remembered and, therefore, can serve as a means of memorizing educational information. Here we see how important it is that in the minds of

schoolchildren not separate, disparate episodes from the history of the development of mathematics are imprinted, but the process of the formation of its basic ideas and methods. Mathematics should appear before schoolchildren in the creative process of creation and development. It is no less important that the history of science allows students to observe in action the interconnection and interdependence of theoretical scientific knowledge and practical human activity. This contributes to a more effective formation of the dialectical-materialistic worldview and scientific thinking of students.

The inclusion of a harmonious system of historical and mathematical information in the process of teaching mathematics, obviously, should mean that the teacher recognizes as legitimate a certain element of amusement and entertainment, which is associated with all sorts of historical curiosities.

But entertaining is permissible not only in primary grades, it can be an easy start to a serious, completely scientific conversation that helps students to master the content of the school course, basic ideas, language, methods of modern mathematical science, methods of creative mathematical activity.

Pedagogy teaches that when presenting new educational information to students, it is advisable to use all ways of forming cognitive interest. An entertaining presentation of new mathematical facts and phenomena, as the practice of the best teachers of mathematics in the country shows, never harmed the subsequent disclosure of their essential properties, and then showing the cause-and-effect relationships, general principles operating in various conditions.

I. Kadyrov quite rightly asserts in his book “The relationship of extracurricular and extracurricular activities in mathematics” (M., Prosveshchenie, 1983) that all or almost all sections of the optional course can and should be studied with the involvement of historical and mathematical material. He distinguishes between several uses of historical material in the process of teaching mathematics:

1. An episodic excursion into the history of mathematics; origin of the term, reference to the discoverer of a formula, theorem or method.

2. A longer conversation, sometimes in connection with the listed elements, for example, a story about the views of the Pythagorean school, solving a historical problem.

3. Review of the life and work of certain outstanding mathematicians (Archimedes, Abu Rayhan al-Biruni, N.I Lobochevsky, etc.).

4. A review of mathematical results obtained in a certain era or related to the development of certain mathematical theories, for example, to computational mathematics and computers.

5. Generalization and systematization of students' knowledge with the help of an in-depth historical review, which analyzes the development of one or another content line of the school course. Of course, there are many more theoretically possible such types. Let's take the grounds for classifying the use of historical material in mathematics lessons:

1) Message - fact, brief historical information.

2) Message - a story about interconnected historical facts, often accompanied by a consideration of illustrative material, analysis and solution of historical problems, etc. (due to which this view is also called conversation).

3) Message - a review that provides an in-depth analysis of the development of a certain branch of mathematics, the formation of its ideas and methods.

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